

STRUCTURAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BIOMEMBRANES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14012532>

Abstract. *This review presents models of biological membranes. It describes the chemical composition and structure of the main membrane components. The key factors influencing the asymmetric distribution of lipids in the membrane are highlighted. It is shown that the plasma membrane possesses unique functions that regulate essential cellular processes, and damage to these processes can lead to cell death.*

Keywords: *membrane, models, lipids, lipid bilayer, rafts.*

The human and animal organism cannot be imagined without cells, and cells cannot be imagined without biomembranes, which separate and preserve the “inner world” of the cell from the external environment. Such isolation of the cell's contents from the external environment is one of the essential characteristics of life. The membrane facilitates the cell's interaction with the environment, selectively allowing many substances to pass through. The plasma membrane (cell membrane, cytoplasmic membrane, plasmalemma) serves as the "arena" for numerous biochemical processes thanks to the many enzymes, proteins, and lipid components (phospholipids, glycolipids, cholesterol, sphingolipids) it contains. The physicochemical properties and structural architecture of the membrane have been so fine-tuned throughout evolution that an effective platform for the functioning of membrane components has been created. Cytoplasmic membranes of all cells determine spatial identity and form the boundary between the intracellular and extracellular spaces (1,2).

Researchers, both of past centuries and present, have been actively studying the properties of lipids and proteins in membranes and proposing theories (models) of membrane structure. For example, in 1773, the active figure and one of the "founders" of the United States, Benjamin Franklin, conducted a series of experiments to measure the area of oil stains on the surface of a pond left by a spoon (5 ml) of spreading olive oil: the stains consistently measured $\approx 2000 \text{ m}^2$. If he had known about the molecular structure of substances at that time, he could have easily calculated the area occupied by a single molecule of oleic acid triglyceride (the main component of olive oil) in this monomolecular stain.

Over a century later, Charles Overton discovered that substances well soluble in lipids could penetrate biomembranes. Therefore, he concluded that the membrane is formed by a thin layer of lipids. It is known that the first membrane model described was obtained from experimental studies of the plasmalemma, where membranes were referred to as erythrocyte shadows. In 1920, the idea of membrane bilayers emerged. I. Gorter and A. Grendel measured the area of extracted lipids from erythrocyte shadows and found that the monolayer of lipids extracted from erythrocyte membranes was exactly twice the area of the cells themselves, leading to the hypothesis of a bilayer lipid organization of biological membranes (7). However, it was noted at that time that the membrane contains a significant amount of proteins, which greatly influence its properties, particularly surface tension. This discovery led to the concept of the "sandwich"

membrane, where the lipid bilayer is enclosed between two protein layers, like a layer of butter in a sandwich.

In 1935, N. Dawson and R. Danielli described the sandwich model of the membrane, where the middle part is represented by a bimolecular layer of lipids, and proteins are located on both its surfaces (13). Several decades (40 years) passed before precise data on the protein-to-lipid ratio in membranes of various cells and modern research methods (such as X-ray diffraction and electron microscopy) disproved this view. In fact, proteins are not surrounding the bilayer but are "embedded" in it, like elements in a mosaic. In 1972, S. Singer and G. Nicolson (20) proposed the fluid-mosaic model of the membrane, in which the membrane consists of a liquid phospholipid bilayer, within which proteins move freely, creating a mosaic pattern. This model was later criticized because not all proteins in the membrane move freely in the liquid lipid layer. According to this theory, the membrane is a lipid "ocean" where protein molecules float. Protein molecules are compared to icebergs floating in the liquid, or more precisely, liquid-crystalline membrane-ocean (7,14). The fluid-mosaic model of membrane structure remains the fundamental principle of biological membrane organization and, despite its shortcomings, is considered the "last classical" membrane theory. Although outdated in some respects, contemporary knowledge and advances in membrane studies are insufficient to revise or update the theory of biological membrane structure.

Despite some flaws, this theory still serves as a fundamental principle for the structure of biological membranes. According to this theory, the membrane is a lipid "ocean" in which protein molecules float like icebergs. The comparison to an ocean arises from the fact that the membrane's aggregate state is liquid (liquid-crystalline), thanks to structural components, particularly lipids. Lipids are amphiphilic molecules, having a polar (hydrophilic) head and a nonpolar (hydrophobic) tail (2). They are poorly soluble in water and tend to form mono- and bilayers due to their amphiphilic nature. The fluidity of membranes is primarily determined by their lipid components: phospholipids, glycolipids, sphingolipids, and cholesterol. Phospholipids in the central part of biomembranes form a bilayer and define the overall state and functional capacity of biomembranes (5,8)

Phospholipids are amphiphilic, consisting of four elements: glycerol, two long hydrocarbon chain fatty acids, phosphoric acid, and a nitrogenous base. Phospholipids vary in the composition of their fatty acids and nitrogenous bases. The most common phospholipid fractions are phosphatidylcholine (PC), phosphatidylethanolamine (PE), phosphatidylserine (PS), phosphatidylinositol (PI), and sphingomyelin (SM). Phospholipids make up more than 60% of the membrane, determining the membrane's properties and functions due to their amphiphilic nature. They have a polar hydrophilic head formed by the nitrogenous base and phosphoric acid and hydrophobic tails formed by fatty acid residues. Sphingolipids also have a polar head and two nonpolar tails but lack glycerol. Sphingolipids consist of one fatty acid residue, one sphingosine residue (two hydrophobic acyl tails), and one polar head residue (a positively charged choline residue and a negatively charged phosphoric acid residue). Cholesterol contains a hydroxyl group at the third carbon atom and an aliphatic branched chain. (9). Glycolipids (11) have one or more sugar residues as a polar head group: N-acetylglucosamine and N-acetylneuraminic acid, while the remaining part is nonpolar (fatty acid residue, sphingosine, D-glucose, and D-galactose). In such a structure (4,8), the interaction of proteins with the hydrophilic heads of phospholipids is

polar, and the interaction of proteins with the hydrophobic tails of phospholipids occurs through hydrophobic amino acids.

Thus, the basis of the plasma membrane is composed of lipids, which, together with cholesterol, form the lipid bilayer, which helps maintain the proper temperature within the membrane necessary to impart membrane fluidity. Membrane fluidity depends on the lipid composition and the temperature of the surrounding environment. Increasing the number of unsaturated fatty acids with double bonds in the membrane lipid composition enhances membrane fluidity. The membrane consists of components that are weakly bonded to each other, allowing them to move within the plane of the membrane, giving the membranes a flexible character, referred to as fluidity. However, the distribution of lipids and proteins in the membrane plane is uneven and exhibits lateral heterogeneity: within the liquid-crystalline phase, microphases appear that do not mix with each other, ensuring the sorting of membrane proteins into various compartments within the same surface, increasing the efficiency of protein interactions (16).

All membranes contain the same components, with small quantitative and qualitative differences. Phospholipids are distributed asymmetrically in the membrane bilayer. For example, in erythrocyte membranes (over 60% of phospholipids), SM (26%) and PC (28%) are located on the outer side of the bilayer, while PS (13%) and PE (27%) are located on the inner side. The membranes of the endoplasmic reticulum contain phospholipids, 85% of which are PC-50-60%, SM-5%, PE-20%, PS-2-8%, and glycolipids account for 2.8%. In the mitochondrial membranes, phospholipids make up 80%, with PS, PE, PI located on the inner membrane, while PH and SM are located on the outer membrane. The asymmetric distribution of lipids in the membrane is maintained by a number of enzymes. For instance, Mg-ATP-dependent aminophospholipid translocase (flipase or ATPase 11) is responsible for the positioning of PS and PE in the inner monolayer of the membrane by transferring these phospholipids from the outer layer to the inner one against the electrochemical potential (19). Flipase activity is inhibited by high concentrations of Ca^{2+} and acetyl phosphate, disrupting phospholipid asymmetry. Phospholipid asymmetry can also be disrupted by the activation of scramblase, which becomes active at high calcium ion concentrations, leading to the movement of phospholipids in both directions (flip-flop). The process of lipid movement in the membrane is hindered because polar heads struggle to pass through the hydrophobic layer. It has been found that lipids on the inner side of the membrane migrate faster than lipids on the outer side. However, if PS appears in the outer layer of the membrane, it enhances the ability of erythrocytes to activate macrophage function (7). The fluidity of the inner monolayer is greater than that of the outer due to the fact that the fatty acid tails of PH and SM are more saturated, making this layer less fluid. The presence of cholesterol in the outer membrane layer reduces the mobility of fatty acids and also reduces the displacement of lipids and proteins, altering their functions. Negatively charged PS, associated with regulatory and structural proteins, when appearing on the outer monolayer, turns into an apoptotic factor, signaling malignant transformation and triggering phagocytosis and blood clotting programs. Additionally, the charge balance on the inner and outer sides of the membrane bilayer changes. The carbon atoms in the hydrocarbon chains of fatty acids are connected by single bonds, around which different segments of the chain can rotate, resulting in the chains adopting various configurations. Due to the bending of the chains, phospholipid molecules acquire a more elongated configuration, leading to an optimal arrangement of all carbon atoms relative to each other. This configuration is called the trans configuration. The alternative to the trans configuration is the gauche

configuration. In membranes, the fatty acid chains are compressed by neighboring molecules, preventing the free form of a phospholipid molecule from being realized. Therefore, in this configuration, the hydrocarbon chain remains extended along the axis (3). It is known that membrane lipids deserve attention for their role in regulating hormonal effects. The regulation of hormonal effects through the adenylate cyclase system is associated with the presence of PI and PS in the membrane. These phospholipids regulate the sensitivity of cyclase to adrenaline, glycogen, and thyroid hormones. The activities of Na⁺, K⁺ -ATPase, Mg²⁺-ATPase, and nucleotidases depend on membrane lipids. It is assumed that the active centers of these enzymes are mainly located on the plasma membrane, and phospholipids interact with the catalytic subunit of the enzymes. PS acts as a cofactor for protein kinases by interacting between the fatty acid chains of PS with the hydrophobic regions of the enzyme. PE and PH affect the activity of the respiratory chain elements, particularly the activity of cytochrome oxidase. PI is involved in ATP formation; PH, PS, and PI participate in the conformation of cytochrome P450 and its role in microsomal oxidation. The functions of lipids in membranes can be summarized into four main types: 1) barrier; 2) participation in the action of hormones and mediators; 3) involvement in membrane transport; 4) influence on enzyme activity.

A number of pathogenic factors lead to changes in the physicochemical and functional properties of membranes, including increased lipid peroxidation (LPO), activation of proteases and phospholipases, a decrease in antioxidants, hypoxia, and so on (6). The induction of LPO results in a disruption of the calcium-transporting function of cells, increasing the permeability of the endoplasmic reticulum membrane for calcium ions through the formation of two types of channels: 1) those localized in bilayer regions of the membrane, referred to as "passive channels" or "peroxide patches," and 2) those localized in the lipoprotein complex of the calcium pump, referred to as "active channels," which depend on the functional state of Ca²⁺-ATPase. The accumulation of calcium ions in the cytosol activates phospholipases, sialidases, and proteases, which degrade phospholipids, glycolipids, and proteins—components of membranes—leading to impaired membrane permeability, cellular metabolism, enzyme leakage into the bloodstream, damage to the protective lipid layer, and the development of immunodeficiency (12).

The lipid component, though fluid, is nevertheless capable of forming partially isolated regions of the bilayer with specific structural properties (21). These regions represent clusters (rafts) of lipid molecules that are highly ordered and solid compared to the surrounding more fluid phase. In the late 1990s, these clusters were termed rafts. This name was given in line with a new theory of biological membrane organization. The existence of two fluid lipid phases becomes possible if the lipid mixture contains at least three components: a "high-melting" lipid (with a melting point above physiological temperature, saturated tails, and a high tendency to form hydrogen bonds with neighboring molecules), as well as cholesterol and sphingomyelin, and a "low-melting" lipid (with a low melting point and unsaturated tails). In the membrane, partially isolated bilayer regions with specific structural properties are formed. These regions represent clusters or "rafts" of lipid molecules that are more ordered and "solid" than the surrounding "liquid phase." These clusters were termed "rafts."

Membrane rafts are small (10-200 nm), heterogeneous, and highly dynamic clusters enriched in cholesterol and sphingolipids. Despite their small size, lipid rafts can constitute a relatively large portion of plasma membranes and perform specific functions. The results obtained to date reveal the prospect of further studies on the functioning of rafts and their involvement in

cell signaling and the regulation of the functional state of cellular membranes. This is necessary to uncover certain links in pathogenesis and to develop effective means of pathogenetic therapy and full-fledged prevention of a number of diseases. Rafts participate in cellular compartmentalization and are stabilized through protein-protein and protein-lipid interactions, forming larger platforms. Rafts are involved in membrane transport. It is believed that rafts play a key role in intracellular protein transport, receptor activity, and signal transmission from receptors to the cytoplasm and nucleus. Some cellular proteins have been identified within the rafts: tyrosine kinase receptors, G-proteins, and T- and B-cell receptors (17,18).

The secretion and delivery of membrane proteins begin in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and stop at the Golgi complex. In this transport, the liquid-ordered phase—rafts—plays a role. There are three different exit sites for vesicles with protein "cargo" from the ER: two are responsible for the transport of secreted and membrane proteins, and the third is the "departure port" for GPI-anchored proteins located inside the rafts. Thus, at the ER stage, these proteins are transported in vesicles similar in composition to rafts, rich in cholesterol and ceramides.

A similar situation occurs with the Golgi complex, from where vesicles move to the membrane, either covered by a clathrin-like protein coat or composed of raft lipids. The raft hypothesis was put forward in connection with the observation of the process of sorting proteins and lipids in the Golgi complex. It was found that vesicles carrying specific proteins are sent to the surface of epithelial cells. It was also established that certain enzymes involved in cholesterol and sphingolipid synthesis are necessary for the delivery of raft proteins to the cell membrane (10, 15). Raft lipids are capable of interacting with bacterial toxins (such as cholera toxins), forming a "doughnut" shape, provoking the formation of "tubules," which underlies the mechanism of virus uptake by cells and the toxic action of these microorganisms. Scientists have discovered that rafts facilitate viral entry into cells.

Their quantity affects the risk of disease development. Drugs that can reduce raft density will become treatments for influenza, HIV, and other viral diseases. Some viruses have an additional supercapsid—a lipid membrane with added proteins—over the protein capsid. Viruses borrow the membrane from the host cell, and the proteins can be either host-derived or viral. When viruses approach a cell, their membrane fuses with the cellular membrane, aiding in viral penetration into the cell.

In this process, specific proteins embedded in their membranes assist in merging with the cell membrane, allowing the virus to anchor to the membrane and initiate fusion and membrane deformation. Rafts interact with viral proteins and play a crucial role in this fusion. It is hypothesized that if a viral fusion protein attacks the cell membrane and a raft is present, it will be easier for the virus to enter the cell.

Thus, both positive and negative signal transmission control is observed (20). In the case of positive control, a raft containing various signaling proteins may cluster or, conversely, act as a safeguard, leading to the movement of components and activation via signaling (19). In the case of negative control, rafts can separate components to block the activation of signaling pathways or suppress the activity of signaling proteins.

If cellular membrane rigidity is increased (e.g., by increasing cholesterol or sphingolipid content), it will hinder viral entry into cells and prevent the development of infectious diseases (influenza, HIV, etc.). Therefore, drugs that lower raft density could serve as treatments for these diseases. In conclusion, lipid rafts shed light on the origin of metabolic disorders in various

pathologies, such as cancer, insulin resistance, inflammation, cardiovascular and infectious diseases, Alzheimer's disease, and others.

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